

ON WEAK FUZZY SUPRA P-SPACES

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Abstract

In this paper, the concept of weak fuzzy supra P-spaces, is introduced and studied. Weak fuzzy supra P-spaces are characterized by means of fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets and fuzzy supra regular F_σ -sets. It is established that fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets in weak fuzzy supra P-spaces are fuzzy supra open but not fuzzy supra dense sets. Also it is obtained that fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets and fuzzy supra regular F_σ -sets in weak fuzzy supra P-spaces are fuzzy supra somewhere dense sets and fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets are not fuzzy supra simply open sets in weak fuzzy supra P-spaces.

1. Introduction

In the year 1965, L. A.Zadeh [13] was first introduced the concept of fuzzy sets and fuzzy set operations in his classical paper. In 1968, the theory of fuzzy topological spaces was introduced and developed by C.L.Chang [4]. In 1983, Mashhour.A.S.et.al., [6] introduced and studied the concept of Supra topological spaces. In 1987, Abd El-monsef et.at [1] introduced the concepts of fuzzy supra topological as a natural generalization of the notion of supra topological spaces. In 1972, Mishra.A.K [7] introduced the concepts of P-spaces as a generalization of ω_α -additive spaces of Sikorski [10] and Cohen.L.W and Goffman.C [5]. The concept of P-spaces in fuzzy setting was introduced by Thangaraj.G and Balasubramanian.G [12]. The concept of fuzzy supra P-spaces was introduced and studied by the author in [9].

In this paper, weak fuzzy supra P-spaces are characterized by means of fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets and fuzzy supra regular F_σ -sets. It is established that fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets in weak fuzzy supra P-spaces are fuzzy supra open but not fuzzy supra dense sets.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 [1].

A collection S^* of fuzzy sets in a set M is called fuzzy supra topology on M if the following conditions are satisfied:

- 1) $\mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{1}$ belongs to S^* .
- 2) $g_\chi \in S^*$ for each $\chi \in \Lambda$ implies $(\bigvee_{\chi \in \Lambda} g_\chi) \in S^*$.

The pair (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra topological space. The elements of S^* are called fuzzy supra open sets and the complement of a fuzzy supra open set is called fuzzy supra closed set.

Definition: 2.2 [8]

Let (M, S^*) be a fuzzy supra topological space and B be a fuzzy set in M , then the fuzzy supra closure and fuzzy supra interior of B defined respectively as

$$cl^*(B) = \wedge \{ g / g \text{ is a fuzzy supra closed set in } U \text{ and } B \leq g \}$$

$$int^*(B) = \vee \{ g / g \text{ is a fuzzy supra open set in } U \text{ and } g \leq B \}$$

Definition: 2.3 [8]

Let (U, T) be a fuzzy topological space and S^* be a fuzzy supra topology on U . We call S^* a fuzzy supra topology associated with T if $T \leq S^*$.

Remark: 2.4 [1]

- (1). Every fuzzy topological space is a fuzzy supra topological space.
- (2). If (M, S^*) is an associated fuzzy supra topological space with the fuzzy topological space (M, S) , then every fuzzy open(closed) set in the fuzzy topological space (M, S) is fuzzy supra open(closed) set in the fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) .

Lemma 2.5 [4]

For a fuzzy set B in a fuzzy topological space M ,

$$(i) 1 - int^*(B) = cl^*(1 - B),$$

$$(ii) 1 - cl^*(B) = int^*(1 - B).$$

Definition 2.6 [3]

A fuzzy supra open set B in fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called fuzzy supra F_σ -set in (M, S^*) if $B = \vee_{i=1}^{\infty} (B_i)$, where $1 - B_i \in S^*$ for $i \in I$,

Definition 2.7 [3]

A fuzzy supra open set B in fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called fuzzy supra G_δ -set in (M, S^*) if $B = \wedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (B_i)$, where $B_i \in S^*$ for $i \in I$.

Definition 2.8 [3]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra dense set if there exists no fuzzy supra closed set D in (M, S^*) such that $B < D < 1$. That is, $cl^*(B) = 1$, in (M, S^*) .

Definition 2.9 [3]

A fuzzy set B in fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra nowhere dense set if there exists no non-zero fuzzy supra open set A in (M, S^*) such that $A < cl^*(B)$. That is, $int^*cl^*(B) = 0$, in (M, S^*) .

Definition 2.10 [3]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra first category set if $B = \vee_{i=1}^{\infty} (B_i)$, where (B_i) 's are fuzzy supra nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) . Any other fuzzy set in (M, S^*) is said to be fuzzy supra second category space.

Definition 2.11 [2]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra boundary of B is defined as $Bd(B) = cl^*(B) \wedge cl^*(1 - B)$. Obviously $Bd(B)$ is a fuzzy supra closed set in (M, S^*) .

Definition 2.12 [3]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra simply-open set if $Bd(B)$ is a fuzzy supra no-where dense set in (M, S^*) . That is., B is a fuzzy supra simply-open set in (M, S^*) if $int^*cl^*[cl^*(B) \wedge cl^*(1 - B)] = 0$ in (M, S^*) .

Definition 2.13 [2]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra semi-open set in (M, S^*) if $B \leq cl^*int^*(B)$; fuzzy supra semi-closed set in (M, S^*) if $int^*cl^*(B) \leq B$.

Definition 2.14 [3]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set if there exists a non-zero fuzzy open set B in (M, S^*) such that $B < cl^*(B)$. That is., $int^*cl^*(B) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) .

Definition 2.15. [11]

A fuzzy set B in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a fuzzy supra regular-open set if $B = int^*cl^*(B)$ and fuzzy supra regular closed set if $B = cl^*int^*(B)$ in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.1. [3]

In the fuzzy topological space

- (a) The closure of a fuzzy open set is a fuzzy regular closed set.
- (b) The interior of a fuzzy closed set is a fuzzy regular open set.

Theorem 2.2. [3]

If A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) if and only if $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) .

Theorem 2.3. [3]

If (A_i) 's ($i = 1$ to ∞) are fuzzy supra somewhere dense sets in a fuzzy supra perfectly disconnected space (M, S^*) , then there exists a fuzzy supra G_δ -set B in (M, S^*) such that $B \leq \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} [cl^*(A_i)]$.

3. Weak Fuzzy Supra P-Spaces

Definition 3.1.

A fuzzy supra topological space (M, S^*) is called a weak fuzzy supra P-space if the countable intersection fuzzy supra regular open sets in (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) . That is., $\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (A_i)$ is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) , where (A_i) 's are fuzzy supra regular open sets in (M, S^*) .

Example 3.1.

Let $M = \{a, b, c\}$. Consider the fuzzy supra sets A, B, C, D and E are defined on M , as follows:

$A: M \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is defined by $A(a)=0.6; A(b)=0.4; A(c)=0.6$;

$B: M \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is defined by $B(a)=0.4; B(b)=0.5; B(c)=0.6$;

$C: M \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is defined by $C(a)=0.5; C(b)=0.5; C(c)=0.5$;

$D: M \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is defined by $D(a)=0.4; D(b)=0.6; D(c)=0.4$;

$E: M \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is defined by $E(a)=0.5; E(b)=0.6; E(c)=0.4$;

Then, $S^* = \{0, A, C, D, A \vee C, A \vee D, C \vee D, A \wedge C, A \wedge D, C \wedge D, 1\}$ is a fuzzy supra topology on M . On computation, $cl^*(A) = 1-D = A$; $cl^*(C) = 1-C = C$; $cl^*(D) = 1-A = D$; $cl^*(A \vee C) = 1-[C \wedge D] = A \vee C$; $cl^*(A \vee D) = 1-[A \wedge D] = A \vee D$; $cl^*(C \vee D) = 1-[A \wedge C] = C \vee D$; $cl^*(A \wedge C) = 1-[C \vee D] = A \wedge C$; $cl^*(B) = A \vee D$; $cl^*(A \wedge D) = 1-[A \vee D] = A \wedge D$; $cl^*(C \wedge D) = 1-[A \vee C] = C \wedge D$; $cl^*(A) = C \vee D$.

Also $int^*[cl^*(A)] = int^*[A] = A$; $int^*[cl^*(C)] = int^*[C] = C$;

$int^*[cl^*(D)] = int^*[D] = D$; $int^*[cl^*(A \vee C)] = int^*[A \vee C] = A \vee C$;

$int^*[cl^*(A \vee D)] = int^*[A \vee D] = A \vee D$; $int^*[cl^*(C \vee D)] = int^*[C \vee D] = C \vee D$;

$int^*[cl^*(A \wedge C)] = int^*[A \wedge C] = A \wedge C$; $int^*[cl^*(A \wedge D)] = int^*[A \wedge D] = A \wedge D$;

$int^*[cl^*(C \wedge D)] = int^*[C \wedge D] = C \wedge D$; $int^*[cl^*(B)] = int^*[A \vee D] = A \vee D \neq B$;

$int^*[cl^*(E)] = int^*[C \vee D] = C \vee D \neq E$.

Thus $A, C, D, A \vee C, A \vee D, C \vee D, A \wedge C, A \wedge D, C \wedge D$ are fuzzy supra regular open sets in (M, S^*) . But B and E are not fuzzy supra regular open sets in (M, S^*) . Now $[A \wedge C \wedge D \wedge (A \vee C) \wedge (A \vee D) \wedge (C \vee D) \wedge (A \wedge C) \wedge (A \wedge D) \wedge (C \wedge D)] = A \wedge D$ and $A \wedge D$ is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) implies that (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P-space.

Now $\text{int}^*(1-A) = D$; $\text{int}^*(1-C) = C$; $\text{int}^*(1-D) = A$; $\text{int}^*(1-[A \wedge D]) = A \vee D$; $\text{int}^*(1-[A \wedge C]) = C \vee D$; $\text{int}^*(1-[C \wedge D]) = A \vee C$. On computation, $[\text{int}^*(1-A)] \wedge [\text{int}^*(1-C)] \wedge [\text{int}^*(1-D)] = A \wedge D$ and $\{\text{int}^*(1-[A \wedge D])\} \vee \{\text{int}^*(1-[C \wedge D])\} \vee \{\text{int}^*(1-[A \wedge C])\} = C$, where $1-A$, $1-C$, $1-D$, $1-[A \wedge D]$, $1-[C \wedge D]$ and $1-[A \wedge C]$ are fuzzy supra closed sets in (M, S^*) . Hence $A \wedge D$ and C are fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets in (M, S^*) . Also $\text{cl}^*(A \wedge D) = 1 - [A \vee D] \neq 1$ and $\text{cl}^*(C) = 1 - C \neq 1$ and thus the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets $A \wedge D$ and C are not fuzzy supra dense sets in (M, S^*) . It is to be noted that the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets $A \wedge D$ and C are fuzzy supra open sets in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.1.

If A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in a weak fuzzy supra P -space (M, S^*) , then

- (i) A is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) .
- (ii) A is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) .
- (iii) A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

(i). Let A be a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Then, $A = \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (\text{int}^*(A_i))$, where $(1-A_i) \in T^*$. Since $(1-A_i)$'s are fuzzy supra open sets, (A_i) 's are fuzzy supra closed sets in (M, S^*) and hence, by Theorem 2.1(b), $[\text{int}^*(A_i)]$'s are fuzzy supra regular open sets in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P -space, $A = \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (\text{int}^*(A_i))$ is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) .

(ii) Since each fuzzy supra regular open set is a fuzzy supra open set in a fuzzy supra topological space. The fuzzy supra regular open set A is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) .

(iii) Since (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P -space, by(ii), the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) . Hence $\text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$ in (M, S^*) . Now $\text{int}^*(A) \leq \text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A)$ implies that $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A) \neq 0$ in (M, S^*) . Hence A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.2.

If B is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in a weak fuzzy supra P -space (M, S^*) , then

- (i) B is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M, S^*) .
- (ii) B is a fuzzy supra closed set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

(i). Let B be a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Then, by Theorem 2.2, $1-B$ is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P -space, by Proposition 3.1.(i), $1-B$ is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) and hence B is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M, S^*) .

(ii). Since each fuzzy supra regular closed set is a fuzzy supra closed set in a fuzzy supra topological space, the fuzzy supra regular closed set B is a fuzzy supra closed set in (M, S^*) .

Remark 3.1.

From the Propositions 3.1 and 3.2, one will have the following: "Fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets in weak fuzzy supra P -spaces are fuzzy supra open sets and fuzzy supra regular F_σ -sets in weak fuzzy supra P -spaces are fuzzy supra closed sets".

It is to be noted that the fuzzy supra G_δ -sets in weak fuzzy supra P -spaces need not be fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets. For, consider the following example:

Example 3.2.

Let $M = \{a, b, c\}$. Let $I = [0, 1]$. Consider the fuzzy supra sets A, B and C are defined on M , as follows:

$A: M \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is defined by $A(a) = 0.4$; $A(b) = 0.5$; $A(c) = 0.6$;

$B: M \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is defined by $B(a) = 0.6$; $B(b) = 0.4$, $B(c) = 0.5$;

$C: M \rightarrow [0,1]$ is defined by $C(a)=0.7; C(b)=0.6; C(c)=0.4;$
 Then, $T=\{0,A,B,C,A \vee B,A \vee C,B \vee C,A \wedge B,A \wedge C,B \wedge C,(A \wedge [B \vee C]),(B \vee [A \wedge C]),(C \wedge [A \vee B]), [A \wedge B \wedge C],1\}$ is a fuzzy supra topology on M . On computation, $A,A \vee B,A \wedge C,A \wedge [B \vee C], B \vee [A \wedge C],C \wedge [A \vee B]$ are fuzzy supra regular open sets in (M,S^*) . Now $[A \wedge (A \vee B) \wedge (A \wedge [B \vee C]) \wedge (B \vee [A \wedge C]) \wedge (C \wedge [A \vee B])] = A \wedge C$ and $A \wedge C$ is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M,S^*) implies that (M,S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P-space. Also $C \wedge (A \vee C) \wedge (A \vee C) = C$ and C is a fuzzy supra G_δ -set but not a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M,S^*) .

The following propositions characterize the weak fuzzy supra P-spaces in terms of fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets and fuzzy supra regular F_σ -sets.

Proposition 3.3.

A fuzzy supra topological space (M,S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P-space if and only if each fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M,S^*) .

Proof.

Suppose that (M,S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P-space and A be a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M,S^*) . Then, by Proposition 3.1(i), the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (X, T) .

Conversely, let each fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set be a fuzzy supra regular open set in the fuzzy supra topological space (M,S^*) . Suppose that (A_i) 's are fuzzy supra regular open sets in (M,S^*) . Then, $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A_i) = A_i$ in (M,S^*) . Let $\text{cl}^*(A_i) = B_i$. Then (B_i) 's are fuzzy supra closed sets in (M,S^*) . Then $\bigwedge_{i=1}^\infty \text{int}^*(B_i)$ is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M,S^*) . By hypothesis, $\bigwedge_{i=1}^\infty \text{int}^*(B_i)$ is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M,S^*) . Thus, $\bigwedge_{i=1}^\infty \text{int}^*(\text{cl}^*(A_i))$ is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M,S^*) . Since $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A_i) = A_i$. Hence $\bigwedge_{i=1}^\infty (A_i)$ is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M,S^*) , where (A_i) 's are fuzzy supra regular open sets in (M,S^*) , implies that (M,S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P-space.

Proposition 3.4.

A fuzzy supra topological space (M,S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P-space if and only if each fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M,S^*) .

Proof.

Let (M,S^*) be a weak fuzzy supra P-space and B be a regular F_σ -set in (M,S^*) . Then, by Theorem 2.2, $1-B$ is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M,S^*) . By Proposition 3.3, $1-B$ is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M,S^*) and hence B is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M,S^*) .

Conversely, let each fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set δ be a fuzzy supra regular closed set in the fuzzy supra topological space (M,S^*) . Suppose that (A_i) 's are fuzzy supra regular open sets in (M,S^*) . Then, $(1-A_i)$'s are fuzzy supra regular closed sets in (M,S^*) . Then, $\text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(1-A_i) = 1-A_i$. Let $\text{int}^*(1-A_i) = \gamma_i$. Then (γ_i) 's are fuzzy supra open sets in (M,S^*) . Then, $\bigvee_{i=1}^\infty \text{cl}^*(\gamma_i)$ is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M,S^*) . By hypothesis, $\bigvee_{i=1}^\infty \text{cl}^*(\gamma_i)$ is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M,S^*) . Then, $1-\bigvee_{i=1}^\infty \text{cl}^*(\gamma_i)$ is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M,S^*) . But, $1-\bigvee_{i=1}^\infty \text{cl}^*(\gamma_i) = \text{cl}^*(\text{int}^*(1-A_i)) = 1-\bigvee_{i=1}^\infty (1-A_i) = \bigwedge_{i=1}^\infty (A_i)$. Hence, $\bigwedge_{i=1}^\infty (A_i)$ is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M,S^*) , where (A_i) 's are fuzzy supra regular open sets in (M,S^*) , implies that (M,S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P-space.

Proposition 3.5.

If A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in a weak fuzzy supra P-space (M,S^*) , then A is not a fuzzy supra dense in (M,S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in the weak fuzzy supra P-space (M,S^*) . Then $(\text{int}^*(A_i))$, where $(1-A_i) \in T$ and Suppose that A is a fuzzy supra dense in (M,S^*) . Then, $\text{cl}^*(A) = 1$, implies that $\text{cl}^*[\bigwedge_{i=1}^\infty (\text{int}^*(A_i))] = 1$. Since

$cl^*[\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(int^*(A_i))] \leq \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} cl^*(int^*(A_i)), \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} cl^*(int^*(A_i)) = 1$. This implies that $cl^*(int^*(A_i)) = 1$. But $cl^*(int^*(A_i)) \leq cl^*(A_i)$ implies that $cl^*(A_i) = 1$, a contradiction to A_i being a fuzzy supra closed set for which $cl^*(A_i) = A_i$. Hence $cl^*(A) \neq 1$ and thus A is not a fuzzy supra dense in (M, S^*) .

Remark 3.2.

In view of the Propositions 3.1 and 3.5, one will have the following: “Fuzzy supra regular G_{δ} -sets in weak fuzzy supra P-spaces are fuzzy supra open but not fuzzy supra dense sets”.

Proposition 3.6.

If B is a fuzzy supra regular F_{σ} -set in a weak fuzzy supra P-space (M, S^*) , then $int^*(B) \neq 0$ in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let B be a fuzzy supra regular F_{σ} -set in (M, S^*) . Suppose that $int^*(B) = 0$ in (M, S^*) . Since B is a fuzzy supra regular F_{σ} -set, by Theorem 2.2, $1-B$ is a fuzzy supra regular G_{δ} -set in a weak fuzzy supra P-space (M, S^*) . Now $cl^*(1-B) = 1 - int^*(B) = 1 - 0 = 1$. This implies that $1-B$ is a fuzzy supra dense set in (M, S^*) , which is a contradiction by Proposition 3.5, that fuzzy supra regular G_{δ} -sets are not fuzzy supra dense sets in a weak fuzzy supra P-space (M, S^*) . Hence $int^*(B) \neq 0$ in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.7.

If B is a fuzzy supra regular F_{σ} -set in a weak fuzzy supra P-space (M, S^*) , then B is not a fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let B be a fuzzy supra regular F_{σ} -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P-space (M, S^*) , by Proposition 3.6, $int^*(B) \neq 0$ in (M, S^*) . Since B is a fuzzy supra regular F_{σ} -set in (M, S^*) , by Theorem 2.2, $1-B$ is a fuzzy supra regular G_{δ} -set in (M, S^*) . Then, $1-B = (\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} (1-B_i))$, where $(1-B_i)$'s are fuzzy supra open sets. Now (B_i) 's are fuzzy supra closed sets in (M, S^*) implies, by Theorem 2.1(b), that $[int^*(B_i)]$'s are fuzzy supra regular open sets in (M, S^*) and hence are fuzzy supra open sets in (M, S^*) . Thus $1-B$ is a fuzzy supra G_{δ} -set in (M, S^*) and then B is a fuzzy supra F_{σ} -set in (M, S^*) . Thus, B is a fuzzy supra F_{σ} -set with $int^*(B) \neq 0$ in (M, S^*) . Hence B is not a fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Remark 3.3.

In View of the Propositions 3.7, one will have the following: “Fuzzy supra regular F_{σ} -sets in weak fuzzy supra P-spaces are not fuzzy supra σ -nowhere dense sets”.

Proposition 3.8.

If A is a fuzzy supra regular G_{δ} -set in a weak fuzzy supra P-space (M, S^*) , then $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra regular G_{δ} -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P-space, by Proposition 3.5, A is not a fuzzy supra dense in (M, S^*) and thus $cl^*(A) \neq 1$, in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P-space, by Proposition 3.1(i), A is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) . Then, $int^*cl^*(A) = A$, in (M, S^*) . Now $int^*cl^*(1-A) = 1 - cl^*int^*(A) = 1 - cl^*int^*(int^*cl^*(A)) = cl^*int^*cl^*(A) = cl^*[int^*cl^*(A)] = 1 - cl^*(A) \neq 0$. Hence $int^*cl^*(1-A) \neq 0$, implies that $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Remark 3.4.

In view of the Propositions 3.1 and 3.8, one will have the following : “Fuzzy supra regular G_{δ} -sets and fuzzy supra regular F_{σ} -sets in weak fuzzy supra P-spaces are fuzzy supra somewhere dense sets”.

Proposition 3.9.

If $A = B \vee C$, where B is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set and C is a fuzzy supra nowhere dense set in a weak fuzzy supra P -space (M, S^*) , then A is a fuzzy supra simply* open set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Suppose that $A = B \vee C$, where B is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set and C is a fuzzy supra nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P -space, by Proposition 3.1(ii), the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) . Hence $A = B \vee C$, where B is a fuzzy supra open set and C is a fuzzy supra nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) , implies that A is a fuzzy supra simply* open set in (X, T) .

Remark 3.5.

In Example 3.2, $A \wedge C$ is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) . Since $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(1-C) = \text{int}^*(1-C) = 0$, $1-C$ is a fuzzy supra nowhere dense set in (M, S^*) and $[A \wedge C] \vee [1-C] = A$ implies that A is a fuzzy supra simply* open set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.10.

If $B \leq A$, where B is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set and A is a fuzzy supra set defined on U in a weak fuzzy supra P -space (M, S^*) , then A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let B be a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M, S^*) such that $B \leq A$, where A is a fuzzy supra set defined on M in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P -space, by Proposition 3.1(ii), the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) and then $\text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$ in (M, S^*) . Now $\text{int}^*(A) \leq \text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A)$, implies that $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . Hence A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.11.

If A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in a weak fuzzy supra P -space (M, S^*) , then there exist a fuzzy supra regular closed set E in (M, S^*) such that $\eta \leq \text{cl}^*(A)$.

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P -space, by Proposition 3.1(iii), the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A is a fuzzy supra somewhere dense set in (M, S^*) and thus $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . Then, there exist a non-zero fuzzy supra open set B in (M, S^*) such that $B \leq \text{cl}^*(A)$. Now $\text{cl}^*(B) \leq \text{cl}^*[\text{cl}^*(A)] = \text{cl}^*(A)$. Since B is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) , by Theorem 2.1(a), the closure of B is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M, S^*) . Let $\text{cl}^*(B) = E$. Hence, for the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A in (M, S^*) , then there exist a fuzzy supra regular closed set E in (M, S^*) such that $E \leq \text{cl}^*(A)$.

Proposition 3.12.

If B is a fuzzy supra regular fuzzy supra F_σ -set in a weak fuzzy supra P -space (M, S^*) , then there exist a fuzzy supra regular open set C in (M, S^*) such that $\text{int}^*(B) \leq C$.

Proof.

Let B be a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Then, $1-B$ is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P -space, by Proposition 3.11, there exist a fuzzy supra regular closed set E in (M, S^*) such that $E \leq \text{cl}^*(1-B)$. Then, $E \leq 1 - \text{int}^*(B)$. This implies that $\text{int}^*(B) \leq 1 - E$. Since E is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M, S^*) , $1 - E$ is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) . Let $C = 1 - E$. Thus there exist a fuzzy supra regular open set C in (M, S^*) such that $\text{int}^*(B) \leq C$.

Proposition 3.13.

If A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in a weak fuzzy supra P -space (M, S^*) , then A is not a fuzzy supra simply open set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P -space, by Proposition 3.1(ii), the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) . Then $\text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$. By Proposition 3.5, the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A in the weak fuzzy supra P -space (M, S^*) , is not a fuzzy supra dense in (M, S^*) and hence $\text{cl}^*(A) \neq 1$. Then, $\text{int}^*(1-A) = 1 - \text{cl}^*(A) \neq 0$. Now $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*[\text{Bd}(A)] = \text{int}^* \text{cl}^*[\text{cl}^*(A) \wedge \text{cl}^*(1-A)] \geq \text{int}^* \text{cl}^*[\text{cl}^*(A) \wedge (1-A)] = \text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A) \wedge (1-A) \geq \text{int}^*(A) \wedge (1-A) = \text{int}^*(A) \wedge \text{int}^*(1-A)$. Since $\text{int}^*(A)$ and $\text{int}^*(1-A)$ are fuzzy supra open sets, $\text{int}^*(A) \wedge \text{int}^*(1-A)$ is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) . Hence $\text{int}^*(A) \wedge \text{int}^*(1-A) \neq 0$ and then $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*[\text{Bd}(A)] \neq 0$. Thus A is not a fuzzy supra simply open set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.14.

If A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in a weak fuzzy supra P -space (M, S^*) , then there exists a fuzzy supra simply* open set α in (M, S^*) such that $F \leq \text{cl}^*(1-A) \vee C$, where C is a fuzzy supra nowhere dense in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P -space, by Proposition 3.1(ii), the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) . Then, $\text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . By Proposition 3.5, the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A in the weak fuzzy supra P -space (M, S^*) , is not a fuzzy supra dense in (M, S^*) and hence $\text{cl}^*(A) \neq 1$. Then $\text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(A) \neq 1$ [otherwise if $\text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(A) = 1$, then $\text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(A) \leq \text{cl}^*(A)$ will imply that $\text{cl}^*(A) = 1$, a contradiction]. Then, $1 - \text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$ and thus $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(1-A) \neq 0$. Then there exists a fuzzy supra open set D in (M, S^*) such that $D \leq \text{cl}^*(1-A)$. Now if γ is a fuzzy supra nowhere dense in (M, S^*) , then $D \vee \gamma$ is a fuzzy supra simply* open set in (M, S^*) . Now $D \leq \text{cl}^*(1-A)$, implies that $D \vee \gamma \leq \text{cl}^*(1-A) \vee \gamma$. Let $F = D \vee \gamma$. Thus, there exists a fuzzy supra simply* open set F in (M, S^*) such that $F \leq \text{cl}^*(1-A) \vee C$ where C is a fuzzy supra nowhere dense in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.15.

If B is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in a weak fuzzy supra P -space (M, S^*) , then $\text{cl}^*(B) \neq 1$ in (M, S^*) .

Proof. Let $B (\neq 1)$ be a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P -space, by Proposition 3.2(i), the fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set B is a fuzzy supra regular closed set in (M, S^*) . Then, $\text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(B) = B$, in (M, S^*) . It has to be proved that $\text{cl}^*(B) \neq 1$ in (M, S^*) . assume the contrary. Suppose that $\text{cl}^*(B) = 1$. Now $\text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(B) = B$, implies that $\text{cl}^*[\text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(B)] = \text{cl}^*(B) = 1$ and then $\text{cl}^* \text{int}^*(B) = 1$, a contradiction to $B \neq 1$. Hence $\text{cl}^*(B) \neq 1$, in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 3.16.

If A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in a weak fuzzy supra P -space (M, S^*) , then $\text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$ in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let $A (\neq 0)$ be a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P -space, by Proposition 3.1(i), the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A is a fuzzy supra regular open set in (M, S^*) . Then $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A) = A$ in (M, S^*) . It has to be proved that $\text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) . Assume the contrary. Suppose that $\text{int}^*(A) = 0$. Now $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A) = A$, implies that $\text{int}^*[\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A)] = \text{int}^*(A) = 0$ and then $\text{int}^* \text{cl}^*(A) = 0$, a contradiction to $A \neq 0$. Hence $\text{int}^*(A) \neq 0$, in (M, S^*) .

4. Weak Fuzzy supra P-Spaces and Other Fuzzy supra Topological Spaces

Proposition 4.1.

If A is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in a fuzzy supra extremally disconnected and weak fuzzy supra P-space (M, S^*) , then $cl^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra clopen set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P-space, by Proposition 3.1(ii), the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra extremally disconnected space, $cl^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) and then $cl^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra clopen set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 4.2.

If A is a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in a fuzzy supra extremally disconnected and weak fuzzy supra P-space (M, S^*) , then $int^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra clopen set in (M, S^*) .

Proof.

Let A be a fuzzy supra regular F_σ -set in (M, S^*) . Then, $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P-space, by Proposition 3.1(ii), the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set $1-A$ is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a fuzzy supra extremally disconnected space, $cl^*(1-A)$ is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) and thus $1-int^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) . Then $int^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra closed set in (M, S^*) . Hence, $int^*(A)$ is a fuzzy supra clopen set in (M, S^*) .

Proposition 4.3.

If (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P-space, then (M, S^*) is not a fuzzy supra hyperconnected space.

Proof.

Let (M, S^*) be a weak fuzzy supra P-space and A be a fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set in (M, S^*) . By Proposition 3.1(ii), the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A is a fuzzy supra open set in (M, S^*) . By Proposition 3.5, the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -set A in the weak fuzzy supra P-space (M, S^*) , is not a fuzzy supra dense in (M, S^*) and hence the fuzzy supra open set A is not a fuzzy supra dense in (M, S^*) , implies that (M, S^*) is not a fuzzy supra hyperconnected space.

Proposition 4.4.

If (A_i) 's ($i=1$ to ∞) are fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets in a fuzzy supra perfectly disconnected and weak fuzzy supra P-space (M, S^*) , then there exists a fuzzy supra G_δ -set E in (M, S^*) such that $E \leq \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} [cl^*(A_i)]$.

Proof.

Let (A_i) 's ($i=1$ to ∞) be fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets in (M, S^*) . Since (M, S^*) is a weak fuzzy supra P-space, by Proposition 3.1(iii), the fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets (A_i) 's are fuzzy supra somewhere dense sets in the fuzzy supra perfectly disconnected space (M, S^*) . Then, by Theorem 2.3, there exists a fuzzy supra G_δ -set E in (M, S^*) such that $E \leq \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} [cl^*(A_i)]$.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, Weak fuzzy supra P-spaces are characterized by means of fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets and fuzzy supra regular F_σ -sets. It is established that fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets in weak fuzzy supra P-spaces are fuzzy supra open but not fuzzy supra dense sets. Also it is obtained that fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets and fuzzy supra regular F_σ -sets in weak fuzzy supra P-spaces are fuzzy supra somewhere dense sets and fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets are not fuzzy supra simply open sets in weak fuzzy supra P-spaces. It is established by means of fuzzy supra regular G_δ -sets that the weak fuzzy supra P-spaces are not fuzzy supra hyperconnected spaces.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this article.

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